

A FRAMEWORK FOR THE ROBOTIC AUTOMATION OF ULTRA-HIGH VOLTAGE CENTER INSPECTION TASKS

Thaleia Flessa^{1}, George Bonias², Angelos Skembris³, Despoina I Makrygiorgou⁴, Dimitris Melissaris⁵*

¹*Castalia Technologies SMPC, Athens, Greece*

²*Castalia Technologies SMPC, Athens, Greece*

³*Castalia Technologies SMPC, Athens, Greece*

⁴*Independent Power Transmission Operator, Research Technology & Development Department, Athens, Greece*

⁵*Independent Power Transmission Operator, Research Technology & Development Department, Athens, Greece*

**thaleia.flessa@castalia.io*

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Abstract

In this paper, we present the development of a framework for the task scheduling system to enable the robotic automation of UHVC (ultra-high voltage center) inspection. Equipment failures at UHVC could be significantly reduced if the inspection methodology allowed for condition-based maintenance (CBM) and the equipment status was systematically monitored. To address this, an autonomous mobile robotic vehicle for inspection using an onboard system of optical and thermal cameras has been developed. The framework enables the automatic determination of the inspection schedule based on a combined time- and condition-criterion, the Total Reliability Index (TRI). The TRI represents the probability of equipment failure based on the evaluation of the images obtained through thermal and optical cameras, as well as the component's age and frequency of inspection, based on its specifications and its importance in the UHVC infrastructure. Depending on the TRI value, a decision is made as to whether a component should be inspected as part of the regular monthly inspection or if it requires more frequent monitoring. The developed framework allows the automated creation of inspection plans on a monthly and weekly basis, based on each component's TRI and without requiring the user's input. The framework also enables the user to create inspection plans that can be saved, modified, and scheduled for immediate or future execution. In all cases, the output of the framework is the list of elements for inspection. The framework enables the execution of systematic, frequent, automated inspections and will lead to financial, administrative and information benefits.

1. Introduction

The Ultra-High Voltage Centers (UHVCs) are critical parts of the Hellenic Electricity Transmission System, and their smooth operation is vital for the uninterrupted transmission and distribution of electrical energy throughout the country. Equipment failures due to regular wear and tear can lead to power outages which might affect large parts of the country. The maintenance of UHVCs is the responsibility of the Independent Power Transmission Operator (IPTO). Systematic and frequent inspection enables the early detection of faults that can lead to failure so that the appropriate action is taken to maintain the equipment before failure occurs. Monitoring the spatial distribution of the temperature of electrical components, alongside optical images of the equipment, is the preferred technique for condition monitoring. Currently, the inspection of equipment is conducted by specially trained IPTO personnel, who utilise thermal and optical cameras to take images of specific components every few months, depending on the type of equipment and manufacturer recommendations. The images are then analysed for signs that indicate faults and maintenance

action is taken when needed. This type of inspection methodology results in time-based maintenance (TBM), where inspection and maintenance activities are scheduled at regular, predetermined intervals based on the equipment's estimated lifespan [1].

An alternative, modern approach is condition-based maintenance (CBM). CBM relies on the fact that it is possible to detect the degradation of electrical equipment at an early stage with appropriate monitoring and maintenance occurs only when specific indicators show decreasing performance which might increase the possibility of an upcoming failure. In contrast to time-based strategies, where maintenance operations take place at regular intervals based on manufacturer recommendations regardless of the equipment's actual condition, in CBM the factor determining the frequency of inspection is the equipment's actual condition, as determined by field inspections [1]. Thus, maintenance activities (e.g., repairs or replacements) are performed only when needed or just before failure. Consequently, CBM has the potential to be substantially more cost-effective than TBM, since maintenance operations take place only when a

component's state warrants it, thus resulting in the optimal allocation of human, material, and financial resources for this task, as well as data-driven financial planning [2]. CBM however requires cost-effective technology to enable the systematic and frequent inspection and automatic processing of the inspection data to achieve this early diagnosis [2].

Currently, regular, and frequent inspections to enable CBM are not feasible for IPTO due to the lack of available technology. Despite the high-level training of IPTO's personnel, TBM is heavily time-intensive and may lead to unnecessary repetitions of field inspections. Consequently, this approach is not effective in achieving the accurate and timely monitoring of UHVC's electrical equipment condition. An autonomous robotic system to increase the granularity of the inspections, as well as the transition from TBM to CBM, is of high importance, considering also that this will be a tool to support the personnel's final evaluation and decision. Therefore, to achieve CBM it is required to introduce new advanced technology that enables the automated inspection of electrical equipment, while at the same time being able to conduct reliable and objective evaluation of the equipment's condition.

The ongoing modernization and the drive towards CBM of power grids using autonomous devices and robotics has resulted in the development of several robotic systems capable of undertaking these inspection tasks. These systems include mobile robots, robots moving along cables and aerial robotics using UAVs and drones [3, 4]. The main tasks that such systems commonly undertake are inspection of equipment, security, and surveillance of the area and, in a few cases, performing maintenance on equipment via an onboard manipulator. The corresponding navigation methods employed are most commonly line following, magnetic guidance, laser, and GPS (where available) [3, 4]. Further examples include a remotely controlled wheeled robot [5], a mobile robot system with a manipulator [6], an autonomous drone-based system [7], a collaborative inspection system consisting of an intelligent sensing unit and a robot that interacts with the unit [8], an all-weather remotely controlled inspection robot [9], and a mobile manipulation system [10].

A different approach is to install thermal cameras on each station component for real-time monitoring [11], which is however costly, since multiple cameras are required, and the solutions need to be accompanied by the necessary telecommunications infrastructure. The installation of cameras and other equipment is inefficient, as in many cases the inspection intervals are in the order of days or weeks, so the monitoring equipment is severely underutilized.

2. Motivation

This need for regular, automated inspections for CBM is the motivation for the ENORASI ("Insight") project. The project aims to develop a robotic solution: an autonomous, unmanned ground vehicle (UGV) that performs inspection of the critical electrical components and equipment of a UHVC using an onboard system of optical and thermal cameras (Figure 1). A UGV instead of a drone is the preferred option for UHVC inspection tasks due to the numerous cables hanging over the

ground above or next to the equipment. These cables carry high loads and are difficult to detect and avoid by the drone, thus the possibility of an accident with severe consequences to the smooth operation of the UHVC cannot be overlooked.

Figure 1: A Robotnik Summit XL UGV used for inspection in ENORASI at a UHVC in Athens, Greece

Inspection is performed autonomously by the vehicle based on a combined time- and condition-based inspection schedule. The schedule is determined through a set of criteria, and the framework that supports this decision-making and task planning is the focus of this paper. Navigation is achieved by an algorithm that requires only a depth estimation sensor and is therefore suitable for deployment even in GPS-denied environments. In this case, depth estimation is achieved via the onboard RGB-D camera and LiDAR [12]. Based on the analysis of the images obtained from the thermal and optical cameras, the condition of each component is evaluated and actions regarding its further monitoring or servicing can be determined. Furthermore, the user has access to all past photographs and their analysis via the user interface, can also perform ad hoc inspections and has the option of operating the UGV remotely in real-time.

This paper presents the development of a framework for the task scheduling system to enable the automation of UHVC inspection tasks. The work is organized as follows: Section 3 presents an overview of the role of the framework and Section 4 discusses the framework design specifications. Section 5 presents the implementation and Section 6 presents the conclusion and future work

3. Framework Overview

The role of the task scheduling framework is to define and schedule the inspection plan for the UHVC. The output of the framework is the list of components to be inspected, which are then passed to the path planner and the navigation system. The main operational specification is the execution of frequent, automated inspections of the UHVC equipment. The thermal and optical component images obtained during each inspection run are assessed to determine each component's condition. Of

paramount importance is determining the current Total Reliability Index (TRI) of each component so that a decision can be made as to whether it should be inspected as part of the monthly regular inspection or is in a degraded state that necessitates more frequent monitoring to ensure that no failure occurs. The TRI represents the probability of equipment failure or malfunction based on the evaluation of the images obtained through thermal and optical imaging, as well as other aggregated data. A challenge that needs to be addressed during the determination of the TRI is that components may exhibit signs of degradation or imminent failure while still operating within specifications, which means that this degradation does not necessarily dictate the immediate replacement of the component. In addition, the progress of this degradation may not be linear, which makes estimating the component's remaining useful lifetime difficult [13, 14].

For the proper implementation of the framework, a web application has been developed (in ReactJs for the frontend and NodeJs for the backend) to schedule and monitor the inspection process of the equipment. The framework allows for the automated generation of inspection plans on a monthly and weekly basis as well as for additional user-generated plans to be executed at specific planned times or ad hoc. The user will be able to view past executed plans, and scheduled plans and create, store and schedule future inspection plans, as well as add or remove additional components for inspection, over the course of an inspection plan's execution. Furthermore, the user will have access to all the data collected from previous inspections, so there will be a record of every component's optical or thermal images acquired during inspection runs, as well as the associated component degradation state automatically determined by the system. The associated data and metadata are stored in a relational database management system (developed in MySQL) and an accompanying image repository. The data will consist of optical and thermal images for every component along with their metadata (such as the exact location, and time the image was acquired), equipment data (name, type, manufacturer, serial number, date of manufacture and installation), as well as other relevant data.

4. Framework Specifications

Currently, inspections are conducted every few months and access to the associated component images and inspection reports are difficult to organize consistently. Therefore, a main requirement is the ability of automated inspection scheduling, based on the automated generation of an inspection plan. The framework specifications for the automated planning of inspections are the following: (1) component types for inspection; (2) TRI definition; (3) component data; (4) automated inspection specifications (time- and condition-based); (5) user-defined inspection specifications.

4.1. Component Types

The component types are the following: circuit breaker (Figure 2), high voltage terminal (bushing, Figure 3), isolator (Figure 4, Figure 5), surge arrester (Figure 6), current transformer, voltage transformer (Figure 7).

Figure 2: Circuit Breaker

Figure 3: Bushing

Figure 4: Open Isolator

Figure 5: Closed Isolator

Figure 6: Surge Arrester with signs of damage

Figure 7: Current and Voltage Transformers

4.2. Total Reliability Index

The TRI represents the overall condition of a component and is the factor determining whether that component needs to be inspected more frequently because it is showing signs of degradation which could lead to failure before the next scheduled maintenance or inspection. The TRI is defined in Eq. (1) and is based on three indices: x_1 is the criticality index, x_2 is the age index and x_3 is the condition index.

$$TRI = x_1 x_2 x_3^2. \quad (1)$$

The values of the criticality index x_1 are in Table 1 and depend on how often each component type needs to be inspected based on the manufacturer's specifications, best practices and its

importance in the day-to-day functioning of the UHVC based (a) on the probability of damage or malfunction and (b) its role in the electrical power supply network of the UHVC. The lower the value of the index x_1 , the more frequent inspections are required.

Table 1: Criticality Index

Type	Inspection Period	Index x_1
Circuit Breaker	1 month	0.25
Current Transformer	12 months	1
High Voltage Terminal	2 months	0.5
Isolator	1 month	0.25
Surge Arrester	2 months	0.5
Voltage Transformer	12 months	1

Index x_2 (Table 2) represents the condition of each component due to ageing and is calculated as the difference in years between the current date and the component's installation date.

Table 2: Age Index

Age Difference	Index x_2
<5 years	1
5-15 years	0.5
>15 years	0.25
Unknown	0.5

The condition index x_3 depends on the component's thermal degradation index $x_{3,th}$ (Table 3) and optical degradation index $x_{3,opt}$. (Table 4). Thermal degradation is determined by analysing the thermal images to detect temperature variations between the component and the environment and between the component and other similar components under similar circumstances. These temperature variations can be signs of issues such as loose connections, overheating, premature wear and tear. A value is assigned between 0 (no degradation detected) and 3 (severe degradation, which indicates a high probability of imminent failure of the component).

Table 3: Thermal Degradation Index

Thermal Degradation	Equipment Status	Index $x_{3,th}$
0 or 1	Good	1
2	Average	0.5
3	Poor	0.25

The optical degradation is determined using an image analysis algorithm to compare current and previous camera images for signs of visible damage. A value of 0 (no visible changes) or 1 (detectable physical change) is assigned to each component.

Table 4: Optical Degradation Index

Optical Degradation	Equipment Status	Index $x_{3,opt}$
0	Good	1
1	Average	0.5

The process of optical inspection is only complementary to that of thermal inspection, therefore thermal degradation is more important. The thermal degradation index and optical degradation index contribute by 70% and 30% to the condition index x_3 , Eq. (2), and the maximum value of x_3 is 1.

$$x_3 = 0.7 \cdot x_{3,th} + 0.3 \cdot x_{3,opt} \quad (2)$$

The age (x_2) and condition (x_3) indices represent condition-based reliability. They describe the component's condition based on natural, age-related wear, and the wear due to the damage already exhibited by the component. Of the three indexes in Eq. (1), the condition index x_3 is the most important, followed by the criticality index x_1 and then the age index x_2 . If a component exhibits a TRI value that is less than a predefined threshold, then it is considered to require immediate inspection and is automatically added to the weekly inspection plan (as described in Section 4.4). The maximum value of TRI is 1.

4.3. Component Data

Component data (Table 5) are stored in a MySQL database.

Table 5: Component Data

Name	Description
ID	Unique component identifier
Type	Type of component
Gate	A or B
Criticality	Value of the Criticality Index x_1
Age	Component age, index x_2
DamageOpt	Optical wear index, calculated based on the most recent inspection images
DamageTherm	Thermal wear index, calculated based on the most recent inspection images
Condition	Normalized & weighted sum of the thermal & optical degradation, index x_3 .
Availability	Availability for inspection (0 or 1)
LastInspect	Date of most recent inspection
TRI	most recent inspection TRI value

4.4. Automated Inspection Specifications

There are two types of automated inspection: weekly and monthly (Figure 8, top center and top right). The plans for the automated inspections are generated automatically, without requiring the user's input. Electrical loads are elevated on weekdays, so all automated inspections are scheduled on specific weekdays, as the additional stress is more likely to lead to a degraded component state. A routine inspection is conducted on all components once per month (Figure 8, top right), regardless of their TRI value – this is the case of time-based inspection. Therefore, the generated monthly inspection plan incorporates all available components. For the case of the weekly inspection (Figure 8, top center), the main inclusion criterion is the weekly calculation outcome of the components' TRI, therefore this is a condition-based inspection. The components with a TRI value below a predefined threshold are

selected for the weekly inspection plan and the minimum number of components is set to one. The weekly automated plan requires no user input; however, the user has the option to add or remove additional components in the weekly inspection plan. The user can also change the day that the monthly and weekly inspections are conducted. For both types of automated inspection, it is expected that the vehicle will be able to complete the inspection within a few hours and that its battery power will suffice to complete the inspection of all components. Should the vehicle need to return to its charging station for any reason (e.g., a depleted battery or other failure to complete the inspection), the completed part of the inspection plan is saved, and an alert is generated regarding the unsuccessful inspection of the remaining components. Once the battery is recharged or the cause of the failure has been determined and removed, the user has the option of completing the run or restarting it from the beginning.

labelled “Scheduling” (bottom left, Figure 9) the user can see all scheduled inspections, as well as the saved inspection plans.

Figure 9: Software Implementation of the Framework

On the top left in Figure 9, a calendar is displayed for the user to review the temporal distribution of inspection runs that have already been scheduled. A component table is displayed on the top right in Figure 9, containing the metadata of each component and the latest TRI indices highlighted in green, yellow and red, and the components’ most recent inspection dates. A set of filters is provided to allow the user to select components based on specific criteria (such as those in Table 5), as the number of components in a UHVC can reach hundreds or even thousands. Selecting components from this list populates the table on the bottom right in Figure 9 for the definition of an ad hoc or unscheduled inspection, which can be saved for a specified date if nothing else is already scheduled or executed immediately if there is no other inspection already in progress or scheduled for the day.

Figure 8: Framework Flow for the Inspection Planning

4.5. User Defined Specifications

The user has the option of defining and scheduling inspections (Figure 8, top left). The user may select available components and may also select components based on several criteria that can be combined (Table 5). For example, the user can select components of a specific type that are above a certain age. The inspection plan is created from the selected components and can be saved for immediate execution or scheduling, provided no other plan is already running or scheduled. The system will execute a saved plan autonomously at the scheduled time, provided no other plan is already being executed.

5. Implementation

Figure 9 illustrates the inspection scheduling process using the framework and its web interface. By “opening” the page

Figure 10: Editing of an Inspection Plan

To modify a saved inspection plan, the user can do so by clicking on its “Plan ID” on the page labelled “Scheduling”

(bottom left, Figure 9), per Figure 8. A pop-up appears (Figure 10) with the modification options for an existing inspection plan (date, adjust components list for inspection). Note that, while the list of components on the bottom right in Figure 9 is populated on a sequential basis, the order in which the components will be inspected is determined by the path planning system module and not the user's order of selection. This is also the case for the automated monthly and weekly inspections. This design choice ensures that the robotic inspection system always chooses the optimal path to conduct inspections, as the path planning criteria are different to the user's order selection criteria.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

The framework developed for the robotic automation of UHVC inspection tasks enables the automated creation of inspection plans on a monthly and weekly basis, based on each component's TRI and without requiring the user's input. The framework also enables the user to create inspection plans based on selected criteria. Each inspection plan can be saved, modified, and scheduled for immediate or future execution. In all cases, the output of the framework is the list of elements for inspection. The framework described in this work will enable the execution of systematic frequent and automated inspections of the equipment condition and will lead to financial, administrative and information benefits: (1) expected cost reduction of maintenance in the period of 15 years due to transferring from TBM to CBM; (2) increased reliability of the UHVCs operation and availability, resulting in increased power grid stability; (3) reduction of consequences due to electrical power failures; (4) data generated by the inspection process via the cameras can be further analysed and lead to an improved understanding of component failure mechanisms and further improve reliability. Future work will focus on extending the framework to include the complete user interface, where the user will be able to also access all available historical data, modify the lower acceptable level of TRI, view live visual feedback of the UGV during an inspection and provide the option for teleoperation. Experiments with the UGV will be carried out to validate the developed approach and assess its real-world performance.

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